

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE REGENT REGULATION OF EAST OGAN KOMERING ULU NUMBER 20 OF 2021 CONCERNING GUIDELINES FOR SOCIAL ASSISTANCE FOR THE POOR IN THE REGENCY OF EAST OGAN KOMERING ULU

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Received: 01 /01/2026 | Revised: 20/01/2026 | Accepted: 10 /02/2026 | Published: 28/02/2026

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the implementation of East OKU Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 concerning grief social assistance in East OKU Regency by assessing the effectiveness of policy implementation at the local government level. The study used a descriptive qualitative method through in-depth interviews, field observations, and documentation studies of policy implementers and beneficiaries. The analytical framework refers to George C. Edward III's policy implementation theory, which emphasizes four main variables: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The results indicate that policy implementation has not been optimal due to obstacles in each implementation variable. The communication aspect still faces obstacles such as a lack of policy socialization, uneven information distribution, and ineffective inter-agency coordination. In terms of resources, limited budget, staff numbers, and technical competencies affect the speed of service. The disposition variable shows differences in commitment, understanding, and attitudes of implementers towards program objectives. Meanwhile, a rigid, procedural, and centralized bureaucratic structure causes slow administrative processes and is less responsive to community needs. Overall, these factors contribute to delays in the distribution of grief social assistance and reduce beneficiary satisfaction levels. This study recommends improving coordination, strengthening human resource capacity, simplifying bureaucratic procedures, and optimizing service information systems to ensure more effective, transparent, and accountable policy implementation. Furthermore, regular data-driven evaluations, consistent internal oversight, and the involvement of communities and local stakeholders in program planning and monitoring processes are needed to ensure policy sustainability, increase public trust, and strengthen the accountability and quality of local government social services. Cross-sectoral collaborative efforts also need to be continuously enhanced.

Keywords: *policy implementation, social assistance for bereavement, policy communication, resources, bureaucratic structure, local government.*

INTRODUCTION

Poverty alleviation is a fundamental government responsibility, realized through adaptive, responsive, and sustainable social protection policies. In the context of decentralization, local governments have a strategic role in designing policy interventions that directly and contextually address community needs. One concrete example of such intervention is the East Ogan Komering Ulu Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for Grief Social Assistance, implemented in East Ogan Komering Ulu Regency. This policy was created as a local social protection instrument aimed at providing financial assistance to underprivileged families experiencing the tragedy of death, thus hopefully alleviating the economic burden while maintaining social stability. This program reflects the local government's efforts to implement policies that are humane, responsive, and oriented towards the real needs of the community. However, policy success is not solely determined by ideal objectives; it also depends heavily on effective implementation on the ground. Public policy implementation is a complex process involving multiple actors, resources, coordination mechanisms, and interacting institutional structures. In practice, social assistance policies for bereavement face diverse administrative and social dynamics, ranging from differences in the capacity

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of village officials to technical challenges in the verification and distribution of aid. Geographical conditions, budget constraints, and the community's level of literacy regarding administrative procedures also influence the smooth implementation of the program. Early indications indicate that the implementation of this policy still faces a number of structural and operational challenges. These issues include potential delays in bureaucratic processes, inconsistent policy interpretations at the implementing level, and suboptimal outreach to beneficiary communities. This situation creates a gap between the normatively designed policy objectives (*das sollen*) and the reality of implementation on the ground (*das sein*). If not addressed systematically, this gap could reduce program effectiveness, undermine public trust in the government, and potentially hinder the achievement of the intended social protection goals.

Therefore, an in-depth analysis of the factors influencing the success of policy implementation is crucial. This study utilizes George C. Edward III's policy implementation framework, which emphasizes four key variables: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. This approach allows researchers to comprehensively examine how inter-actor coordination, the adequacy of human and financial resources, implementer commitment, and the bureaucratic system influence the performance of social assistance policies for bereavement. Thus, the study is expected to provide an in-depth empirical overview of the dynamics of policy implementation at the local level. Furthermore, the analysis results are expected to not only provide academic contributions to the development of public policy implementation studies but also serve as practical evaluation material for local governments in improving the quality of social services. The resulting recommendations can serve as the basis for refining coordination mechanisms, strengthening apparatus capacity, simplifying administrative procedures, and increasing program transparency and accountability. With continuous improvement measures, it is hoped that the social assistance policy for bereavement will be more effective, more targeted, and provide tangible benefits to communities in need.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Preliminary studies on the implementation of social assistance policies indicate that the success of a social protection program is determined not only by the quality of the policy design but also by the effectiveness of its implementation in the field. Various national studies confirm that the implementation of social assistance programs in Indonesia still faces challenges in terms of policy communication, limited resources, inter-agency coordination, and differences in understanding among implementers at the local level (Ahdiyana & Sukmawati, 2023; Saragih et al., 2023; Wahyudi, 2023). Research by Munawir et al. (2019) on poverty alleviation programs found that weak coordination and limited human resources were the main obstacles to achieving policy targets. Similar findings were also presented by Bedasari and Wahyuni (2020), who emphasized that the success of social services is greatly influenced by the capacity of the apparatus and the effectiveness of communication between the government and beneficiaries.

At the international level, various policy implementation studies highlight the importance of adaptive and responsive public administration processes to local social conditions (Grindle, 1980; Pressman & Wildavsky, 1973). Lipsky (1980), through the concept of street-level bureaucracy, explains that implementing actors in the field play a significant role in determining how policies are translated into practice. Meanwhile, Sabatier and Mazmanian (1980) emphasize that policy implementation is influenced by program design, the socio-political environment, and the capacity of implementing organizations. Quah's (2019) study in the ASEAN region also shows that rigid and inflexible bureaucratic structures often slow down public service delivery and reduce the effectiveness of social policies.

In the context of social assistance policies, research by Putong and Wahyudi (2022) and Kurniawati et al. (2022) highlights the importance of clear bureaucratic communication patterns to ensure targeted and timely aid distribution. Furthermore, research by Nugroho et al. (2021) shows that poverty alleviation programs in Indonesia require a strong coordination system, accurate databases, and consistent oversight to ensure policy implementation achieves public welfare goals. A study by Listiana et al. (2025) also emphasizes that data-driven monitoring and evaluation are crucial tools for identifying implementation barriers and improving the quality of social services. Theoretically, policy implementation research largely draws on George C. Edward III's implementation framework, which emphasizes four key variables: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. This model emphasizes that policy success depends on the clarity of information delivery, the adequacy of human and financial resources, the commitment of implementers, and the organizational systems that support the administrative process. Furthermore, Van Meter and Van Horn's (1975) framework highlights the importance of policy standards and the characteristics of implementing organizations, while Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983) emphasize the interaction between institutional factors and the social environment in determining implementation

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success. Thus, the literature review shows that the implementation of social assistance policies is a multidimensional process involving various actors, bureaucratic mechanisms, and social conditions. Barriers such as ineffective communication, limited resources, differing attitudes among implementers, and complex bureaucratic structures are factors frequently identified in various studies. Therefore, a comprehensive theoretical approach and in-depth empirical analysis are essential to understanding the dynamics of social assistance policy implementation at the local level and formulating strategies for sustainable improvement.

The first variable is communication, which emphasizes the importance of transmitting clear, accurate, and consistent policy information from policymakers to implementers. Clarity of policy objectives and standards must be uniformly understood by all parties involved. In the context of social assistance for bereavement, communication effectiveness is measured by the extent to which local governments successfully disseminate guidelines, procedures, and recipient criteria to village officials and targeted poor communities. Failure in this aspect can lead to misinterpretation and inaccurate implementation. The second variable is resources, which encompass essential elements for implementing the policy. Resources are not limited to financial budgets but also include competent staff, relevant information, adequate authority, and supporting facilities. The implementation of this Regent's Regulation is highly dependent on the availability of aid funds, the sufficient number and expertise of social service staff, and the technological infrastructure for verifying population data. A deficiency in any of these resources could significantly hamper the smooth distribution of aid to the poor.

The third variable, disposition, refers to the attitudes or tendencies of policy implementers. Successful implementation is heavily influenced by the willingness and commitment of bureaucrats to implement the program in accordance with its stated objectives. If implementers have a positive outlook and support for the social assistance for bereavement policy, they will tend to implement it diligently. Conversely, rejection or indifference from officials at the sub-district and village levels can be a major obstacle, preventing the policy from being implemented effectively and providing maximum benefits to the target community. The final variable is bureaucratic structure, which relates to the characteristics of the implementing organization. This aspect includes clear standard operating procedures (SOPs) and a coordinated division of authority between work units. A complex and fragmented bureaucratic structure can hinder implementation, while a streamlined and integrated structure will facilitate it. An analysis of the implementation of this Regent's Regulation will examine how the SOPs for aid distribution are developed and how coordination between the Social Services Agency and lower-level government agencies operates to ensure efficient processes without overlap.

METHOD

1. Types and Approaches of Research

This research employs a qualitative approach with a descriptive approach. This method was chosen because it is relevant for describing and analyzing in depth the implementation of Regent Regulation of East Ogan Komering Ulu Number 20 of 2021. Qualitative research allows researchers to understand the complexity of the processes, interactions, and meanings behind the implementation of the social assistance policy for bereavement in its natural context. Through a descriptive approach, this study aims to present a systematic, factual, and accurate picture of the factors influencing the policy's success or failure based on Edward III's theoretical framework, without statistical manipulation or hypothesis testing. The approach used in this research is a case study. This approach is considered most appropriate because the research focus is singular and in-depth, namely on the specific implementation of Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 in East Ogan Komering Ulu Regency. Case studies allow researchers to conduct an intensive investigation into the real-world context of the policy, exploring how communication variables, resources, dispositions, and bureaucratic structures interact uniquely within the local administrative and social environment. Thus, a holistic and comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of policy implementation can be effectively achieved.

2. Location and Time of Research

This research was conducted in East Ogan Komering Ulu (OKU) Regency, South Sumatra Province. The location selection was purposive, based on the consideration that this regency is the primary locus and jurisdiction of the policy being studied, namely Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021. Specifically, the research focused on several key agencies directly involved in the implementation process. These agencies include the East OKU Regency Social Service as the main coordinator, as well as several sub-district and village offices selected to obtain a more representative and in-depth picture of implementation at the field level. The determination of more specific locations at the sub-district and village levels was carried out by considering the relevance and representativeness

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of data related to policy implementation variables. The selection criteria were based on considerations such as poverty levels, the number of registered bereavement social assistance recipients, and the dynamics of coordination between village governments and the Social Service. This selection aimed to capture variations in policy implementation, both in areas showing relatively smooth implementation and in areas facing significant challenges. Thus, the collected data is expected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the supporting and inhibiting factors in the implementation of the Regent Regulation.

3. Research Informants

The informants in this study were selected using purposive sampling. This method was chosen because it was considered most appropriate for capturing individuals with in-depth knowledge, relevant experience, and direct involvement in the implementation of Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021. The primary criterion for selecting informants was their capacity to provide rich and accurate information in accordance with Edward III's research variables. Informants were classified into two main groups: key informants, who came from the ranks of policy makers and those responsible for policy implementation, and supporting informants, who were implementers at the field level and beneficiary communities. Key informants in this study consisted of officials with strategic authority and responsibility in implementing the social assistance policy for bereavement. They were the Head of the East OKU Regency Social Service, the Head of the Social Protection and Security Division, and the Head of the Section that technically handles verification and distribution of assistance. Their selection was based on their central positions in the process of policy formulation, dissemination, resource allocation, and oversight. Information from these key informants was essential for gathering in-depth data on aspects of communication, bureaucratic disposition, and bureaucratic structure from the perspective of policymakers. Supporting informants were selected to complement and verify information obtained from key informants and to gain insight into implementation at the grassroots level. This group included sub-district heads, village heads, and village officials tasked with facilitating aid applications in their respective areas. In addition, several families receiving bereavement assistance were also involved as informants. Their involvement was crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of information transmission, the perceived adequacy of resources, and the responses and challenges directly faced by the target community during the application and receipt process of the bereavement assistance.

4. Data collection technique

The primary data collection technique in this study was semi-structured in-depth interviews. This method was chosen to gather comprehensive and flexible information regarding informants' perceptions, experiences, and interpretations of the implementation of Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021. The researchers used an interview guide based on the four variables of Edward III's theory to ensure all crucial aspects were covered. Questions were posed to key informants and supporters to explore communication effectiveness, resource availability, implementer disposition, and constraints within the bureaucratic structure. The entire interview process was recorded using an audio recorder and supported by field notes. In addition to interviews, researchers also used non-participant observation techniques to enrich the primary data. Observations were conducted directly at several key locations, such as the Social Services Office and the village offices that served as the research sample. The observations focused on the service flow for applying for bereavement social assistance, interactions between officials and the community, and the availability of supporting facilities and infrastructure for policy implementation. The purpose of these observations was to verify interview data, understand the social context surrounding the implementation process, and capture phenomena or behaviors not disclosed by informants. Observation notes were systematically documented in field notes. To complement the primary data, secondary data collection techniques were conducted through documentation studies. This method aimed to collect written data and official documents relevant to the implementation of the bereavement social assistance policy. The documents reviewed included the draft of Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021, technical implementation instructions, standard operating procedures (SOPs), budget realization reports, aid recipient data, and request letters from the community. Analysis of these documents is crucial for understanding the formal framework of the policy, verifying resource allocation, and assessing consistency between written regulations and implementation practices in the field.

5. Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique in this study adopted the interactive model developed by Miles and Huberman, which consists of three simultaneous activity streams. The first stage is data reduction, which is the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, and abstracting raw data obtained from interview transcripts, field notes, and

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documents. The collected data were then systematically classified and coded based on the four main variables of Edward III's theory: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. This process aims to sharpen the analysis, remove irrelevant information, and organize the data so that final conclusions can be drawn and verified. The second stage is data display, where the reduced set of information is presented in an organized manner to enable conclusions to be drawn. Data presentation in this qualitative research is not limited to narrative text but also utilizes matrices and charts to facilitate understanding. For example, matrices will be used to map findings related to communication barriers faced by various levels of implementers, from the Social Services Agency to village officials. Through this systematic data presentation, researchers can identify patterns of relationships between variables and understand the dynamics of the implementation of social assistance policies for bereavement more comprehensively. The final stage is conclusion drawing and verification. At this stage, researchers interpret the presented data to answer the research questions regarding the implementation of the Regent's Regulation. The initial conclusions drawn will be continuously tested for accuracy throughout the research through a verification process. Verification is carried out by reviewing field notes, triangulating data sources between interviews, observations, and documentation, and searching for consistent patterns. This step is crucial to ensure that the conclusions drawn are highly credible and supported by strong evidence from the field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Overview of the Implementation of Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 in East OKU Regency

The implementation of East OKU Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 has generally been underway since its enactment, with the primary goal of providing a social safety net for poor residents experiencing grief. This policy is designed to ease the financial burden on bereaved families through the provision of cash assistance. The process begins with an application submitted by heirs at the village level, which is then verified through a series of steps up to the Social Services Agency. Conceptually, this process is intended to ensure that assistance is appropriately targeted according to the criteria stipulated in the regulation. Initial field observations indicate that the implementation of this policy exhibits varying dynamics across regions. The Social Services Agency, as the primary coordinator, has strived to fulfill its mandate, but coordination with the government at the sub-district and village levels remains a crucial factor in determining the smoothness of the process. Village officials' understanding of procedures and budget availability are key determinants of the speed of response to residents' requests. The interaction between communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure is beginning to emerge as crucial elements for the program's success.

The East OKU Regency Social Services plays a central role as the final validator and executor of aid distribution. However, its effectiveness is highly dependent on the performance of village and sub-district officials, who serve as the frontline. They are the first to receive applications, conduct initial verification of complete population administration documents, and determine the poverty status of prospective recipients. The quality of data submitted from this lower level significantly impacts the accuracy and speed of decision-making at the agency level, indicating inter-agency interdependence. From the perspective of the target community, the response to this bereavement social assistance policy has been generally positive. Many beneficiary families feel the program has greatly helped them during this difficult situation. However, public awareness and understanding of the application procedure are uneven. Some residents still rely on word of mouth or rely entirely on the initiative of village officials. This phenomenon indicates that the policy's socialization has not optimally reached all levels of the poor population eligible for benefits. The implementation overview reveals several fundamental challenges that need to be addressed. The main obstacles identified include the sometimes time-consuming population data verification process, limited technical understanding at the village level, and potential delays in fund disbursement due to budget allocation constraints. These issues serve as the starting point for a more in-depth analysis using the Edward III framework to identify the root causes of each policy variable that impacts the effectiveness of grief assistance distribution.

2. Analysis of the Effectiveness of Communication of Grief Social Assistance Policy

Analysis of communication variables indicates that the transmission of policy information from the Social Services Agency to sub-district and village governments has been implemented, but not optimally. Interviews with several village heads revealed that initial socialization was conducted formally through circulars and limited meetings. However, these activities were not accompanied by in-depth technical guidance, leading to differing interpretations regarding the completeness of administrative requirements. Consequently, many village officials still had to repeatedly contact the agency for confirmation, slowing down the initial application process from the community. The lack of clarity in policy messaging is another obstacle. Although the Regent's Regulation outlines

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the criteria for poverty, implementation in the field shows ambiguity. Informants from village officials reported difficulties in verifying the poverty status of prospective recipients who are not registered in the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS), yet their actual conditions are extremely poor. The lack of clarity in operational standards for such cases creates doubt among implementers at the grassroots level, potentially hindering access for families who are entitled to receive bereavement assistance.

The consistency of information delivery was also highlighted. Interview data with beneficiary families revealed that the information they received was often inconsistent. Some residents received complete information from the hamlet head, while others only heard from neighbors with varying details, particularly regarding the amount of assistance and disbursement timing. This inconsistency created confusion and misplaced expectations within the community, indicating that the communication channel from the village government to the target community was not yet standardized. The effectiveness of direct outreach to the target community was identified as still very low. The study found that the East OKU Regency Government tended to rely on village officials as the sole information channel. There was no extensive outreach effort through other media such as local radio, banners in strategic locations, or public announcements. The reliance on word-of-mouth communication methods meant that not all eligible poor residents were aware of the program, resulting in suboptimal participation and policy reach. Finally, the lack of formal feedback channels is a significant communication weakness. Neither village implementers nor communities have a clear mechanism for submitting complaints, questions, or feedback regarding implementation challenges. When problems arise, resolutions tend to be case-by-case and personal, involving direct contact with department officials. This absence of structured two-way communication channels hinders the ongoing evaluation and improvement of policies, potentially leading to recurring problems.

3. Availability and Utilization of Resources in the Distribution of Grief Social Assistance

An analysis of financial resources indicates that the budget allocation for grief assistance is often insufficient to meet all requests received within a single fiscal year. Interviews with Social Service officials confirmed delays in disbursing funds from regional coffers, which directly impacts the delay in aid distribution to heirs. These budget limitations and uncertainty are major obstacles, forcing recipient families to wait long periods, thus reducing the policy's effectiveness as a rapid response to grief. From a human resources perspective, the Social Services Department found that the number of staff tasked with verifying application documents was very limited. The high workload disproportionate to the number of available personnel, resulting in a backlog of documents and a time-consuming verification process. Although staff possess adequate competencies, the limited number of staff presents a significant obstacle. This slows down the workflow from verification to final approval, ultimately delaying the right of poor people to receive social assistance for bereavement. The availability of accurate information, particularly regarding population data and the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS), is a crucial issue. The study found frequent data mismatches between village government data and reference data at the Social Services Department. The process of verifying poverty status becomes complicated and lengthy due to the need for manual cross-validation. This limited access to integrated and up-to-date data significantly hampers policy implementation, particularly in ensuring accurate targeting of aid recipients as mandated by regulations.

The authority of implementers at the village level has been identified as extremely limited. Village officials serve only as recipients and forwarders of application files, lacking the authority to make initial decisions, even for clearly eligible cases. All verification decisions are centralized within the Social Services Agency, creating a rigid and slow bureaucracy. This lack of discretion or limited authority at lower levels makes the process inflexible, especially when dealing with the unique circumstances of poor residents who are not formally registered. Resources in the form of supporting facilities, particularly technological infrastructure, are inadequate and unevenly distributed. Many village offices lack stable internet access or adequate computer equipment to support digital administrative processes. As a result, submission of application files is often carried out manually and conventionally. This gap in facilities creates inefficiencies and slows the flow of information from villages to the Social Services Agency, indicating that facilities and infrastructure are a weak point in the implementation chain of social assistance policies for bereavement.

4. Disposition and Commitment of the Implementers of the Grief Social Assistance Policy

Analysis of dispositions at the Social Services Agency level indicates a strong, positive commitment to the policy's objectives. Interviews with relevant officials revealed that the bereavement assistance program is viewed as a crucial humanitarian mandate to protect the poor. However, this supportive attitude is often hampered by the reality of limited resources. Consequently, despite strong intentions to expedite the process, agency implementers

often feel frustrated by the inability to respond to requests as quickly as expected, which indirectly impacts morale and work ethic. At the village level, the disposition of implementers showed significant variation. Some village officials demonstrated a high level of commitment by proactively assisting residents in completing documents and overseeing the process through to the agency. However, others tended to be passive, viewing this task as an additional administrative burden without clear incentives. This attitude was influenced by their level of understanding of the policy and the complexity of existing procedures. The lack of technical support and clarity from the district level often weakened their motivation to implement the policy optimally. The tendency of implementers to reject or accept the policy was strongly influenced by their perception of the program's effectiveness. In-depth interviews indicated that when village officials saw that aid was being successfully distributed and providing tangible benefits to their residents, their disposition became more positive. Conversely, when they consistently faced bureaucratic obstacles, rejected documents, and complaints from the community, skepticism and even subtle rejection began to emerge. This manifested itself in slowness in processing new applications from residents seeking bereavement assistance.

A cognitive conflict was found among lower-level implementers, affecting their disposition. On the one hand, they have a strong desire to assist bereaved families in accordance with social and humanitarian norms. On the other hand, they are bound by rigid administrative regulations, such as the requirement for prospective recipients to be registered in the DTKS (National Data and Information System). This dilemma often leaves village officials feeling powerless and frustrated, ultimately eroding their commitment to strictly enforcing the rules, sometimes even seeking loopholes to assist residents. Official appointments and incentives are important determinants in shaping implementer disposition. This study found no specific incentive system, either financial or non-financial, for village officials handling the social assistance program for bereavement. Carrying out this task is considered a routine function without additional rewards. This lack of a reward mechanism has the potential to weaken the long-term commitment of implementers, reducing policy implementation to merely fulfilling bureaucratic obligations rather than a service initiative grounded in empathy and dedication.

5. The Impact of Bureaucratic Structure on the Smooth Implementation of Grief Social Assistance

An analysis of the bureaucratic structure shows that existing Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) tend to be rigid and inflexible. While SOPs provide certainty, their inability to accommodate unique situations on the ground, such as those involving poor people outside the DTKS (Disaster Mitigation Center), poses a major obstacle. This overly procedural structure forces village-level implementers to reject files that are substantively valid but do not meet strict administrative requirements. Consequently, workflow slows down and the policy's goal of responding quickly to grief fails to achieve its objectives. The organizational fragmentation between the Social Services Agency, sub-district governments, and village governments creates significant coordination challenges. Each level of the bureaucracy operates in separate silos with vertical and formal communication channels. Complete reliance on physical file transfers between agencies without the support of an integrated digital system results in a very slow verification process.

This fragmented structure lengthens wait times for applicants, demonstrating that inter-unit coordination is a weak point in the smooth implementation of the social assistance policy for bereavement. The highly centralized bureaucratic structure poses a serious obstacle to implementation. All authority for final verification and approval rests with the Social Services Agency of East OKU Regency, while village officials function solely as document collectors and forwarders. The lack of delegation of authority at lower levels means that every request, no matter how small, must navigate a lengthy bureaucratic chain. This makes the system unresponsive and slow, as frontline implementers lack the discretion to expedite processing for cases that clearly meet the criteria. The complex bureaucratic process, which spans from villages to sub-districts to social services offices, inherently slows aid distribution. Each application must pass through multiple desks and verification stages at each level of government. This lengthy structure contradicts the urgency of grief assistance, which should be provided as quickly as possible to ease the burden on families. This complex bureaucratic chain effectively delays the policy's benefits, transforming what should be a rapid response program into delayed and less relevant assistance. The existing bureaucratic structure also weakens accountability. With a lengthy process involving multiple parties, it becomes difficult to pinpoint the specific point where delays occur. When people inquire about the status of their applications, responsibility is shifted between agencies, from the village to the sub-district to the government agency. This structure creates a diffusion of responsibility, weakening oversight and making it difficult for the public to obtain reliable information, thus reducing public trust in the effectiveness of the bereavement assistance program.

CONCLUSION

Based on George C. Edward III's analysis of the implementation model, it can be concluded that the implementation of East OKU Regent Regulation Number 20 of 2021 has not been optimal. All four variables exhibit significant interrelated obstacles. The communication variable is hampered by uneven socialization and the absence of feedback mechanisms. The resources variable is a crucial issue due to budget constraints, a lack of implementing staff, inaccurate data, and a lack of authority at the village level. Implementer disposition varies and tends to decline due to bureaucratic constraints, while a rigid and centralized bureaucratic structure is a major obstacle. Negative interactions between these variables undermine the effectiveness of this social assistance policy for bereavement. The fragmented and centralized bureaucratic structure is exacerbated by a lack of human resources and technology, creating a slow and inefficient workflow. This condition directly erodes the disposition or commitment of implementers at lower levels, who become frustrated by complicated procedures. Furthermore, inconsistent communication fails to bridge the gap in understanding between institutions and between the government and target communities, thus reinforcing an unresponsive implementation cycle that falls far short of the policy's initial expectations. Essentially, this research found a significant discrepancy between the policy's normative objectives and the reality of its implementation on the ground. The noble intention to provide rapid and targeted assistance to the grieving poor was undermined by systemic obstacles across all four dimensions of implementation. As a result, assistance that should have been responsive and urgent often ended up being delayed. Failures to manage communications, allocate adequate resources, maintain implementer commitment, and design a flexible bureaucratic structure have prevented the effectiveness of this Regent's Regulation from achieving its maximum results.

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